

Clinical Spectrum of Anemia in Early Pregnancy at a Tertiary Care Hospital

Sushma V. Dev¹, Shwetha H.², Shreya Vaidya³, Ashwini V. Shenoy⁴, Vinaya M. Hoogar⁵

¹Professor and Unit Chief, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute, Mysuru, Karnataka, India

²Third Year Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute, Mysuru, Karnataka, India

³Second Year Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute, Mysuru, Karnataka, India

⁴First Year Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute, Mysuru, Karnataka, India

⁵First Year Junior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Mysore Medical College and Research Institute, Mysuru, Karnataka, India

Received: 27-10-2024 / Revised: 24-11-2024 / Accepted: 23-12-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Shwetha H.

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Anemia in pregnant women is significant health problem in India. Etiology is varied and diagnosis and management of anemia in pregnancy is challenging due to physiological changes in pregnancy.

Aims and Objectives:

1. To categorize anemia in early pregnancy.
2. To study the severity of anemia in early pregnancy.

Methods: Women in early pregnancy visiting Cheluvamba Hospital OPD, Mysuru with hemoglobin < 11 g% were included in study from December 2023 to May 2024. Demographic details, details of clinical history and anemia work up were entered.

Results: 100 pregnant women were diagnosed to have anemia in early pregnancy. Mean age was 22.6 years. Normocytic normochromic anemia was seen in 74% of pregnant women followed by microcytic hypochromic anemia (23%) and dimorphic anemia (3%). 4 pregnant women had beta thalassemia trait followed by 1 case each of HPFH or double heterozygous for HPFH and delta beta thalassemia, Hb D with Hb S trait and Hb E trait. Mean Hemoglobin level (8.5g% vs. 9.7g%), MCV (67.6 vs. 78.4) and MCH (19.2 vs. 27.4) was significantly less in pregnant women with hemoglobinopathy as compared to pregnant women without hemoglobinopathy ($p < 0.002$, $p < 0.023$ and $p < 0.039$ respectively).

Conclusion: In addition to nutritional anemia, thalassemia poses a major challenge in pregnant women. Screening of pregnant women for thalassemia should be incorporated in national health program to prevent morbidity and mortality associated with thalassemia.

Keywords: Anemia, Pregnancy, Iron deficiency, Thalassemia, Red Blood Cell indices, Hemoglobin electrophoresis.

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Introduction

Anemia in pregnant women accounts to significant health problem in developing countries like India. Anemia is one of the major indirect causes of maternal deaths in developing countries. In spite of many health programmes implemented in India, prevalence of anemia in pregnancy continues to be an epidemic.[1]

Anemia is defined as a condition where the number or oxygen carrying capacity of red blood cells are inadequate to meet the physiological demands of the body.

According to Centre for disease control (CDC), anemia is defined as hemoglobin level less than 11 gram/dl in first and third trimester and hemoglobin level <10.5 gram /dl in second trimester. Etiology of anemia depends on factors like geographical location, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, iron stores and effects of iron supplementation. The diagnosis and treatment of anemia in pregnancy is affected by physiological changes in pregnancy and presence of underlying hematological disorders.[2] WHO has estimated that prevalence of anemia in pregnant women is 14 % in developed countries

and 51 % in developing countries. In India, prevalence of anemia is 65 to 75 %. [3] In Karnataka, prevalence of anemia in pregnant women is 47.6%. [4] Prevalence of hemoglobinopathy like thalassemia in India is reported in certain communities like Sindhis, muslims and certain tribal groups with the prevalence varying between 8 to 10 %.[2]

Thalassemia is an autosomal recessive disorder involving impaired production of globin peptide chain during hemoglobin synthesis resulting in anemia. It is estimated that around 80-90 million people are carrying beta thalassemia gene in the world with nearly 60,000 carriers born every year.[2] South East Asia contributes to 50% of the entire burden of beta thalassemia carriers of the globe and India lies in the thalassemic belt of the world.[5]

The present study is carried out to know the clinical spectrum of anemia in early pregnancy at a tertiary care hospital.

Aims and Objectives

1. To categorize anemia in early pregnancy.
2. To study the severity of anemia in early pregnancy.

Materials and Methods

After obtaining the Institutional Ethics Committee's permission EC REG: ECR/134/Inst/KA/2013/RR-19, Ref No: MMC EC 78.23 IS and written informed consent from the pregnant women fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled for the study. A prospective observational study was carried out on pregnant women in first trimester visiting antenatal OPD at Cheluvamba Hospital, Mysuru over a period of 6 months from December 2023 to May 2024.

Inclusion Criteria: Women in early pregnancy visiting antenatal OPD at Cheluvamba Hospital, Mysuru with hemoglobin less than 11 gram / dl and willing to give written informed consent were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Pregnant women in second and third trimester of pregnancy, postpartum mothers, pregnant mothers with history of blood transfusion in the past 3 months and pregnant mothers not willing to give written informed consent were excluded from the study.

Demographic details, details of thai card, detailed history including age, occupation, socioeconomic status, gravid status, spacing between pregnancies, abortions, stillbirth, menstrual history for history of heavy menstrual bleeding, diet history any history of repeated blood transfusion, family history of hemoglobinopathies and examination details were entered in case recording proforma. The following

investigations were done which includes, blood group and Rh typing, complete blood count including red blood cell indices. For patients with hemoglobin value less than 11 gram / dl, peripheral blood smear, serum ferritin, serum retic count and hemoglobin electrophoresis was done. In case of hemoglobinopathies, hemoglobin electrophoresis of patient's husband was done.

Statistical Analysis

Collected data is analysed using SPSS 22.0 statistical software. Descriptive and inferential statistical analysis were used. For results on continuous measurements Mean +/- Standard deviation and results on categorical measurements as number (%). Significance was assessed at 5% level of significance. Student t test used to find the significance of study parameters on continuous scale between 2 groups on metric parameter. t test used to compare means of two groups. Chisquare / Fischer exact test used to find significance of study parameters on categorical scale between 2 or more groups.

Results

A total of 100 pregnant women with anemia in early pregnancy were enrolled in the study. 87 % of pregnant women belonged to 20 – 24 years of age. Mean age was 22.6 years. 94% of pregnant women had secondary school education.

Normocytic normochromic anemia was seen in 74% of pregnant women followed by microcytic hypochromic anemia (23%) and dimorphic anemia (3%). Abnormal hemoglobin electrophoresis was noted in 7 pregnant women with anemia at first antenatal visit. Out of 7 cases of hemoglobinopathy which was diagnosed, 4 pregnant women had beta thalassemia trait followed by 1 case each of HPFH or double heterozygous for HPFH and delta beta thalassemia, Hb D with Hb S trait and Hb E trait (table 2)

There is clinically significant difference in the severity of anemia ($p < 0.001$) noted in the present study (Table 3). There is also significant history of repeated blood transfusion in pregnant women with hemoglobinopathy as compared to anemia due to other causes ($p < 0.04$).

There is significant difference in the hematological indices in the present study. The mean hemoglobin level (8.5g% vs. 9.7g%), mean corpuscular volume (67.6 vs. 78.4) and mean corpuscular hemoglobin (19.2 vs. 27.4) was significantly less in pregnant women with hemoglobinopathy as compared to pregnant women without hemoglobinopathy ($p < 0.002$, $p < 0.023$ and $p < 0.039$ respectively).

Serum ferritin (ng/ml) was significantly higher in hemoglobinopathy group (197.5) as compared to no hemoglobinopathy group. (40.7) $p < 0.001$.

Abnormal liver function test was seen in 2 pregnant women with hemoglobinopathy. Total bilirubin (mg/dl) was 1.8, 2.63 and Direct bilirubin (mg/dl) was 0.7 and 1.05. Hepatosplenomegaly was also

noted in the present study. 4 pregnant women with anemia had mild splenomegaly, followed by 1 each with mild hepatosplenomegaly and moderate splenomegaly (19 cm).

Table 1: Age distribution of pregnant women with anemia in early pregnancy

Age in Years	No. of Patients	%
20-24	87	87.0
25-29	8	8.0
30-34	4	4.0
35-39	1	1.0
Total	100	100.0

Mean ± SD: 22.69±2.63

Table 2: Distribution of hematological parameters in pregnant women with hemoglobinopathy

Hemoglobinopathy	Hb%	MCV (fl)	MCH (pg)	MCHC	PCV (%)	PBS	S.Ferritin (ng/ml)	Hb F (%)	Hb A (%)	Hb A2 (%)	Others
Beta thalassemia trait	9.5	72.4	21.3	33.9	32.2	NNA	56.5	0.90	94.1	5	5
Beta thalassemia trait	9.4	62.2	19	30.2	31.1	NNA	145	1.5	92	5.8	5
Beta thalassemia trait	8.8	53.8	8.3	34	25.9	MHA	21	1	93	5.6	5
Beta thalassemia trait	8.5	63.4	21.5	21.5	33.9	MHA	56	0.9	94	5	5
HPFH or double heterozygous for HPFH and delta beta thalassemia	8.4	82.7	23.8	34	22	MHA	221	878	12.2	<11	40%
Hb D with Hb S trait	5.7	67	18.6	27.8	20.5	DMA	823	1	95.7	3	Hb D – 1.1
Hb E trait	9.5	72	22	34	33	NNA	60	1.1	70.7	28	5

Hemoglobin% (Hb%), Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC), Packed cell volume % (PCV%), Peripheral blood smear (PBS), Serum Ferritin (S.Ferritin),

Fetal Hemoglobin (HbF), Adult Hemoglobin A (Hb A), Adult Hemoglobin A2 (Hb A2), Normocytic normochromic anemia (NNA), Microcytic hypochromic anemia (MHA), Dimorphic anemia (DMA).

Table 3: Distribution of severity of anemia in pregnant women in early pregnancy

Severity of Anemia	Hemoglobinopathy		Total
	No	Yes	
Mild	50(53.8%)	0(0%)	50(50%)
Moderate	43(46.2%)	6(85.7%)	49(49%)
Severe	0(0%)	1(14.3%)	1(1%)
Total	93(100%)	7(100%)	100(100%)

P≤0.001**, Significant, Fisher Exact Test

Table 4: Association of clinical variables of anemia in pregnant women in early pregnancy

Variables	Hemoglobinopathy		Total	P Value
	No	Yes		
OBSTETRIC SCORE				
• Primigravida	57(61.3%)	5(71.4%)	62(62%)	0.706
• Multigravida	36(38.7%)	2(28.6%)	38(38%)	
MARRIED LIFE (years)				
• 1-5	90(96.8%)	6(85.7%)	96(96%)	0.255
• >5	3(3.2%)	1(14.3%)	4(4%)	
COMPLAINTS				
• Nil	84(90.3%)	6(85.7%)	90(90%)	1.000
• Yes	9(9.7%)	1(14.3%)	10(10%)	

Tiredness	9(9.7%)	1(14.3%)	10(10%)	
HISTORY OF BLOOD TRANSFUSION				
• No	93(100%)	5(71.4%)	98(98%)	0.004**
• Yes	0(0%)	2(28.6%)	2(2%)	
Total	93(100%)	7(100%)	100(100%)	
Chi-Square Test/Fisher Exact Test				

Table 5: Comparison of hematological parameters of anemia in early pregnancy in relation to hemoglobinopathy

Variables	Hemoglobinopathy		Total	P Value
	No	Yes		
Age (Years)	22.66±2.56	23.14±3.8	22.69±2.64	0.640
BMI (kg/m ²)	22.28±1.28	23.57±1.2	22.37±1.31	0.011*
Hb g%	9.74±0.93	8.54±1.34	9.65±1	0.002**
MCV (fl)	78.42±12.03	67.64±9.2	77.66±12.14	0.023*
MCH (pg)	27.49±10.33	19.21±5.13	26.92±10.26	0.039*
MCHC	32.19±2.82	30.77±4.76	32.09±2.98	0.226
PCV %	29.51±5.22	28.37±5.52	29.43±5.22	0.581
RDW %	17.79±4.41	20.4±2.95	17.97±4.36	0.128
S.Ferritin(ng/ml)	40.72±39.75	197.57±284.13	51.7±89.32	<0.001**

Body Mass Index (BMI), Hemoglobin % (Hb%), Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin (MCH), Mean Corpuscular Hemoglobin Concentration (MCHC), Packed cell volume % (PCV%), Red cell distribution width (RDW), Serum Ferritin (S.Ferritin).

Discussion

In developing countries like India, anemia during pregnancy significantly contributes to maternal morbidity and mortality.[7] In our study, 87 % of pregnant women with anemia in early pregnancy were in the age group of 20 – 24 years and mean age was 22.6 years. Similar results are reported in a study done by Bhatt P et al [8], Virender G et al [9] and Mishra RK et al [2] and pregnant women with anemia belonged to 20 – 25 years. In the present study, pregnant mothers with anemia had screening for hemoglobinopathies at first antenatal visit itself and prevalence of hemoglobinopathy was 7% and anemia due to other causes was 93%. In studies done by Bhatt P et al [8], prevalence of anemia in pregnant mothers was 53.6% but it was considerably higher in studies done by Virender et al [9] (84.9%), Toteja et al [10] (84.9%). In national family health survey 4 (NFHS-4) conducted during 2015-16 found an overall prevalence of 50.3% among pregnant women.[11] Community screening for anemia in adolescent girls is essential as majority of Indian women enter pregnancy in anemic status.

In the present study varying degree of severity of anemia in pregnant women in first trimester were noted. Mild anemia was (50 %), moderate anemia (49 %) and severe anemia (%).

Similar results are seen in a study done by Bhatt P et al [8] where mild anemia (41.5%) and moderate

anemia (51.2%) are comparable. Severe anemia (1%) was less in our study as compared to 7.3% in a study done by Bhatt P et al. [8]

In the present study, 74% of pregnant women had normocytic normochromic anemia, followed by microcytic hypochromic anemia (23%) and dimorphic anemia (3%) which is different from the study done by Bhatt et al [8] and Nirmala et al [12] where hypochromic microcytic peripheral smear picture was seen in 65.7% and 69.2%, respectively. Normocytic normochromic anemia was 74 % in the present study while normocytic picture was seen in 37.2% women in study done by Bhatt et al [8]. Iron deficiency contributes to majority of cases of anemia and several studies have established the nutritional cause of anemia in pregnant women. National programs should be further intensified to prevent anemia in pregnant women in India.

In the present study, 7 cases with hemoglobinopathy were diagnosed in the first antenatal visit in first trimester itself. 4 pregnant women had beta thalassemia trait followed by 1 each of Hb D with Hb S trait, Hb E trait and 1 with HPFH or double heterozygous for HPFH and delta beta thalassemia. In a study done by Ruangvutilert P et al [13], annual report of Siriraj hospital, almost 50% of pregnant women were affected by thalassemia trait, including alpha thal – 1 trait, beta thal trait and HbE trait. In a study done by Sharma A et al [14], they detected 14 case of beta thalassemia trait, 3 cases of HbD Punjab, 1 case of HbE and HbS trait and 2 cases of delta beta thalassemia which is similar to our study. In a study done by Balgir et al [15], found sickle cell trait 7.45%, followed by beta thalassemia trait 2.89%, hemoglobin E trait 0.24% and sickle cell disease 1.68%. In a study done by Torress LDS et al [16], 70 cases of type D hemoglobin from southeast brazil were diagnosed, out of these, 66 (94.3%) had

Hb D – Punjab, 8(12.1%) had heterozygous Hb S/D – Punjab and 58(87.9%) had heterozygous Hb A/D – Punjab.

In addition to nutritional anemia, hemoglobinopathy, thalassemia poses a major health challenge for pregnant women. Confirming the case of iron deficiency still predates the diagnosis as these two conditions still coexist at the same time in an individual. Patients not responding to iron therapy may be a case of thalassemia.

In our study, 6 pregnant women with hemoglobinopathy had moderate anemia and 1 of them had severe anemia. In a study done by Torres LDS et al [16], 47.11% of pregnant women had different grades of anemia with a range falling in between 45% to 66%. Frequency of severe anemia was seen to be 8.33% in beta thalassemia trait, 9.32% in normal, 19.35% in sickle cell trait and 71.3% in homozygous sickle cell disease in pregnant women. In a study done by Patel KD et al [17], prevalence of hemoglobinopathy was 5.8% mainly sickle cell trait 94.48%. 50.34 % had moderate anemia while mild and severe anemia were seen in 44.8% and 4.82%, respectively. HPFH is clinically asymptomatic, but interaction of delta beta thalassemia with beta thalassemia can result in a severe disorder. HPFH was one of the hemoglobinopathy seen in our study. Hence early screening for hemoglobinopathy in first trimester itself can prevent severity of anemia in pregnancy.

In various regional studies done in anemia in pregnant women, hemoglobinopathies were seen. In a study done by Gunda P et al [18], in Telangana, out of 2478 antenatal mothers screened for hemoglobinopathies, 3.05% and 4.5% were detected for hemoglobinopathies from MGMH and PHCs respectively. Beta thalassemia was predominant with a frequency of 2.15% from MGMH and 2.9 % from PHCs. In a study done in large maternity hospital in Mumbai [19], 270 of them were thalassemia carriers and 22 had other hemoglobinopathies. In a study done by Bhukhanvala et al [20], prevalence of beta thalassemia was 3.385 and 1.5% of them were sickle cell anemia among antenatal 14 women. In our study, 1 case of HPFH or Double heterozygous for HPFH and delta beta thalassemia was seen. In a multicentric study done in six cities in India, by Mohanty D et al [21], the overall prevalence of beta thalassemia trait was 2.78% and varied from 1.48 to 3.64 % in different states. HbE trait was seen in Dibrung in Assam (23.9%) and Kolkata in West Bengal (3.92%). delta beta thalassemia, HPFH, HbS trait, HbD trait, HbE homozygous and HbE beta thalassemia as well as HbS homozygous and HbS – beta thalassemia (<1%) were also identified. Marriages in India are usually among individuals of the same caste, and this makes it important to know the prevalence of thalassemia and HbE. This is the

first large study in India to show the prevalence of delta beta thalassemia and HPFH. Interaction of delta beta thalassemia with beta thalassemia can result in severe disorder and identifying these conditions is important for genetic counselling.

Conclusion

Maternal anemia complicates pregnancy outcomes. In addition to nutritional anemia, hemoglobinopathy, pose a major health challenge in pregnant women. Complete blood count with red blood cell indices and iron status should be performed in all pregnant women in first trimester itself to assess not only their anemic status, but also to allow for assessment of the risk of hemoglobinopathy, including thalassemia. Confirming the case of iron deficiency anemia still predates the diagnosis and patients not responding to iron therapy may be a case of thalassemia. There should be mass screening program at tertiary care hospitals to identify women with hemoglobinopathy. This would lead to increased reproductive options to the females in terms of partner decision, prenatal diagnosis, and medical termination of pregnancy in tertiary care centres where facilities are available.

Therefore, a high level of antenatal care and collaboration between obstetricians and hematologists is essential to improve pregnancy outcome and prevent adverse pregnancy complications. Screening of pregnant women for thalassemia should be incorporated as a national health program to prevent morbidity and mortality associated with thalassemia.

Authors Contribution

Dr. Sushma V. Dev – Definition of intellectual content, literature survey, manuscript preparation, implementation of study protocol, editing, submission of article.

Dr. Shwetha H. – Manuscript preparation, data collection, data analysis and revision.

Dr. Shreya Vaidya – Data collection, literature survey, editing.

Dr. Ashwini V. Shenoy – Data collection.

Dr. Vinaya M. Hoogar – Data collection

Source of Funding: NIL

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